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ENTREPRENEURIAL MINDSET AND RESILIENCE IN DRIVING GLOBAL HUMAN RESOURCE COMPETENCE WITHIN INDONESIA'S INDUSTRIAL SECTOR: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF SELF-EFFICACY

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to examine the influence of an entrepreneurial mindset and resilience on global human resource competence (GHRC), with self-efficacy functioning as a mediating variable. This research is specifically conducted to address the existing gap regarding the factors that shape global human resource competencies within Indonesia's industrial sector. 697 respondents participated in the study from various sub-sectors of industries in Indonesia. The purposive sampling technique was employed, focusing on employees with a minimum of two years of work experience. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the SmartPLS 4 software was used for analyzing the data. The findings indicate that entrepreneurial mindset has a significant effect on global human resource competence. However, the direct effect of resilience on global human resource competence was not supported. Self-efficacy was also found to have a significant direct effect on global human resource competence and mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and global human resource competence. The findings are crucial for industrial workers to meet global challenges. As a limitation, the sampling method was based on the purposive sampling technique and was not limited to industrial subsectors, ensuring a comprehensive representation across industries. Only three endogenous constructs – entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and self-efficacy – were examined. Future research should employ more comprehensive technique sampling and include other crucial factors affecting global human resources competence, such as leadership, environment, and other contextual factors. The findings of this study contribute to enriching the theoretical notion that entrepreneurial mindset and self-efficacy act as critical factors that impact global human resources competence. The research also contributes to elucidating that personal resilience does not directly enhance global human resource competency; instead, it can bolster self-efficacy, which in turn elevates that competency. The result reasonably supports the idea that self-efficacy plays a fully mediating role in the model.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurial Mindset, Resilience, Human Resources, Self-Efficacy, Global Era, Competitiveness.

JEL Classification: L26, M53, J24, D91, O15.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intense competition and transformative changes in the global era, characterized by VUCA conditions—namely Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity (Vermeulen & Hémond, 2025)—require the industrial sector to possess competent human resources (HR) with strong competitive advantages (Barney, 2000). Therefore, organizations must develop human resources who not only demonstrate technical expertise but also possess the ability to adapt, innovate, and remain resilient under pressure (Luthan & Youssef, 2007). Under such conditions, technical skills alone are insufficient to ensure organizational excellence; consequently, HR must also possess essential soft skills, including adaptability to change, resilience in the face of pressure and failure, and the capacity to innovate in order to generate relevant and value-added solutions (Alhijris & Albaz, 2024). These capabilities are critical for building robust, agile, and globally competitive organizations. This perspective aligns with Human Capital Theory, which emphasizes the importance of investing in individual talents to enhance long-term organizational efficiency and performance (Becker, 2009).

Numerous elements can enhance HR preparedness for the global landscape from management sectors (Groenewald et al., 2024; Osabutey et al., 2015) to social capital (Mäkelä et al., 2012; Reniati et al., 2024). The entrepreneurial mindset (Mawson et al., 2023) and resilience are considered as two significant factors that impact global HR competencies (Frederick et al., 2016). The entrepreneurial mindset, characterized by innovation, proactivity, and risk taking, has historically been linked to an individual's capacity to devise creative solutions in the face of uncertainty (Widhajati, 2024). While resilience allows human resources to recuperate from setbacks and adjust to environmental alterations (Brown & Williams, 2015; Nelson et al., 2007).

Several studies have explained that an entrepreneurial mindset contributes to the enhancement of entrepreneurial mentality in dealing with market uncertainty (Widhajati, 2024), entrepreneurial intention (Jiatong et al., 2021), and business performance (Do et al., 2022; Mubarak et al., 2019). However, research examining the direct effects of these variables on the development of global human resource competence among employees in the industrial sector remains limited, despite evidence suggesting that an entrepreneurial mindset serves as a driving force for the creation of successful born-global strategies (Vaivode, 2022).

Moreover, Self-efficacy is considered a conduit that translates entrepreneurial orientation and resilience into tangible action. Research conducted by (Jiatong et al., 2021) indicates that entrepreneurial mindset exerts a substantial influence on entrepreneurial intention when bolstered by elevated self-efficacy. Luthans et al. (2007) similarly discovered that resilience is correlated with performance alone when individuals possess sufficient self-confidence. The researchers contend that self-efficacy serves as a pivotal mediator among various significant variables, including the relationship between meaning in life and subjective well-being (X. Wang et al., 2021), goal orientation and performance (Magni et al., 2021), social relationships and depressive symptomatology (Fiori et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2022), as well as stressful life events and depressive symptoms (Maciejewski et al., 2000; Zuo et al., 2020), among others. This discovery reinforces the assertion that self-efficacy serves as a psychological mechanism enhancing the influence of entrepreneurial mindset and resilience on global human resource competencies (GHRC).

Although previous studies examining entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and self-efficacy have been widely conducted, most of this research remains fragmented, as each variable has generally been investigated in isolation. Studies that integrate these three variables simultaneously within a single analytical model are still scarce. Moreover, empirical research linking entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and self-efficacy to global human resource competence (GHRC) is virtually nonexistent, particularly within the industrial sector in Indonesia. Therefore, to address this research gap, the present study incorporates these three variables into a unified model and examines their effects on global human resource competence (GHRC).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1. *Entrepreneurial mindset and global human resources competence*

There isn't one definition that can fully describe the entrepreneurial mindset (EM). But you can explain it by looking at its main traits: a person's view of the world that emphasizes creativity and innovation in the face of problems, making decisions with limited information to reach specific goals (Daspit et al., 2023). In today's competitive world, having an entrepreneurial mindset (EM) is very important. This is because globalization, digitalization, and more competition around the world are all changing the way people work and do business very quickly (Singh, 2024). A strong

mindset helps people be flexible, creative, and able to spot chances even when things are uncertain. People with an entrepreneurial mindset (EM) are innovative and proactive. They don't just wait for opportunities to come up; they also come up with new solutions that meet the needs of society and business. This means that having an entrepreneurial mindset is essential for staying relevant and competitive in a changing world (Pidduck et al., 2023). Several studies have shown that entrepreneurial mindset (EM) makes managers more creative and flexible in a fast-paced and competitive workplace (Nobre, 2002). This helps improve global human resources competence (GHRC) because it encourages new ideas, ways to solve problems, and the use of new opportunities around the world (Corrêa et al., 2022; Kraus et al., 2012). So, based on the earlier explanation, the statement is put forward as a hypothesis:

H1: Entrepreneurial mindset has a positive impact on global human resource competencies.

2.2. Resilience and its impact on global human resource competence

Resilience is generally defined as a person's fortitude in dealing with many problems they face in life, such as stress and pressure that occur in the workplace and in everyday life (Pradhan & Kumar, 2021). Resilience is a part of psychological capital that significantly contribute to improving HR performance (Cantante Rodrigues et al., 2021) and lets people stay productive and competent (Occhipinti et al., 2023) even on the most chaotic and high-pressure days (Schmitt & Chan, 2014).

People who are resilient can handle stress, get back up after failing, and keep going even when things are hard. Given these skills, it's not unexpected that he was able to deal with a number of difficult issues in the global globe, like changes in technology, variations in culture, and changes in the market that happen one after the other (Dahlgaard & Anninos, 2022). Resilience is an important trait that helps people stay productive, mentally secure, and competent at work when things go rough in the global world. Based on the reasons given above, the assertion is put forward as a hypothesis:

H2: Resilience has a positive impact on global human resource competencies.

2.3. Entrepreneurial mindset impact on Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy (SE) is often defined as a person's confidence in planning and executing the steps necessary to achieve specific performance goals (Bandura, 2023). Self-efficacy is a crucial

psychological construct for human resource development, especially in an increasingly competitive global marketplace (Akmalia et al., 2023), as it enables individuals to face global challenges flexibly, confidently, and with self-motivation. One way to enhance self-efficacy is through an entrepreneurial mindset (EM).

The relationship between an entrepreneurial mindset and self-efficacy has been clearly demonstrated by several studies. (Vaivode, 2022) asserts that an entrepreneurial mindset can encourage individuals to evaluate themselves positively, motivate them to take calculated risks, and conceptualize failure as an essential element of the learning experience. This statement is reinforced by (Deniz & Tasgin, 2024) who argue that an entrepreneurial mindset, in turn, drive individuals become more confident, thus encouraging creative thinking, initiative, and a focus on finding solutions. By adopting this mindset and action, individuals will become more confident in their ability to handle problems, complete tasks, and exploit new opportunities. Therefore, as proposed by (Aboobaker & KA, 2023), an entrepreneurial mindset can be a driving force that psychologically influences an individual's ability to improve and strengthen self-efficacy in various performance situations in a globalized world. Based on the reasons mentioned above, this statement is established as a hypothesis:

H3: Entrepreneurial mindset has a positive effect on self-efficacy.

According to Bandura (1977, 2023), self-efficacy is closely related to an individual's psychological strength in assessing their ability to organize and execute the necessary actions to manage future situations. This trait is believed to be a fundamental element in human resource development (Chaudhary et al., 2012), especially in the context of competitive globalization. Human resource professionals with high self-efficacy demonstrate greater readiness to face global challenges (Valbusa et al., 2025) because they are more confident in handling complexity, tolerate uncertainty, and can make adaptive and strategic decisions (Waddington, 2023). Within the framework of Social Cognitive Theory, self-efficacy influences an individual's thinking, motivation, resilience to stress, and choice of actions in a constantly changing environment (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998).

Conversely, self-efficacy requires resilience because an individual's belief in their abilities cannot develop strongly without the capacity to recover from failure and stress (Schwarzer & Warner, 2013).

Self-efficacy is formed through experiences of overcoming challenges (Waddington, 2023). However, these experiences are often characterized by obstacles, failures, and uncertainty. Without resilience, individuals are more likely to give up when faced with difficulties, thus missing out on the successful experiences needed to build high levels of self-efficacy (Siddique et al., 2023).

Empirical research supports the positive influence of self-efficacy on individual preparedness in professional and global contexts. For example, studies by Al-Jubari et al. (2021) and Guan et al. (2013) show that self-efficacy is significantly related to proactive personality and career adaptability (Hou et al., 2014). Several studies also indicate that individuals with high levels of self-efficacy demonstrate more effective decision-making (Li et al., 2022), employability (Wallin et al., 2021), improved self-esteem (Ismail, 2017), and improved task performance (Sameer et al., 2019). They also demonstrate superior cross-cultural communication skills and a tendency to proactively respond to global change. This finding is supported by research by Newman et al. (2019), which found that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of developing work competencies based on a global mindset. Therefore, we can assert that self-efficacy serves as a key determinant of global human resource competency, strengthening psychological capacity and driving superior work behavior. Drawing from the aforementioned explanation, we can formulate several hypotheses:

H4: Resiliency has a positive effect on self-efficacy.

H5: Self-efficacy has a positive effect on global human resources competence.

2.4. The mediating role of self-efficacy

Global human resource competency (GHRC) is a critical determinant of corporate and national competitiveness in the global landscape. An

entrepreneurial mindset significantly enhances individual competency in navigating global dynamics (Pennetta et al., 2025). Conversely, psychological resilience, defined as the capacity to bounce back from stress and adversity, serves as a crucial foundation for enhancing individual resilience in unpredictable circumstances (Gupta & Govindarajan, 2002). However, these two variables often operate indirectly, requiring mediation by internal psychological mechanisms such as self-efficacy. As explained by Bandura (2023), self-efficacy is a crucial mediating variable linking personal traits (such as an entrepreneurial mindset and resilience) to individual or organizational performance. As shown by several previous studies, individuals with a strong entrepreneurial mindset will have strong self-efficacy (Jiatong et al., 2021), have the capacity for innovation (Bodolica & Spraggon, 2021), and respond adaptively in their careers (Guan et al., 2013), while also demonstrating greater resilience to competitive pressures (Newman et al., 2019). Similarly, psychologically resilient individuals often develop self-efficacy by overcoming adversity, thereby increasing their confidence in managing global competitive scenarios (Schwarzer & Warner, 2013). Self-efficacy serves as a psychological channel that transforms potential into actual capabilities in the global competitive landscape. Consequently, in the context of human resource development in the global era, it is important to examine the mediating effect of self-efficacy between an entrepreneurial mindset and resilience in relation to human resource capabilities. Therefore, the previous discussion provides a basis for formulating this statement as a hypothesis:

H6: Self-efficacy mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and global human resources competence.

H7: Self-efficacy mediates the relationship between resilience and global human resources competence.

Figure 1: Research Framework.

Note: Solid lines denote direct paths, while dashed lines indicate indirect (mediated) relationship.

Source: Model developed by researchers.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A quantitative methodology with an explanatory research design was employed that aims to test causal relationships between various variables (Sainani, 2014). The causal relationships were used to determine the impact of entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and self-efficacy on global human resources competence (GHRC). This study also aims to assess the mediating effect of self-efficacy in the relationship between entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and GHRC. This methodology is used because it allows researchers to test theories empirically using quantitative data. This study uses a cross-sectional strategy, where data is collected at specific points to evaluate the structural model using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 4 program (Hair Jr et al., 2014).

This study involved human participants. Participation in the online survey was voluntary, informed con-sent was obtained prior to participation, and responses were collected anonymously and treated with strict confidentiality.

3.1. Demographics and cohort

This study examined the employee population in Indonesia's globally competitive industrial sector, encompassing multinational corporations, technology-based startups, and internationally focused service industries. The sampling method used was a non-probability purposive sampling technique, focusing on employees with at least two years of work experience, particularly because the total population of the industrial sector remains

undefined (Saunders et al., 2003). A total of 697 participants completed the questionnaire satisfactorily. According to the criteria (Hair Jr et al., 2014) for PLS-SEM analysis, the sample size should be at least ten times the number of indicators. Although this guideline provides a practical heuristic, it should not be considered a strict statistical requirement, and recent studies recommend complementing it with additional considerations such as statistical power considerations. Studies by (Sarstedt et al., 2022) indicate that sample sizes above 100 are generally sufficient to detect medium effect sizes with a statistical power of 0.80 in PLS-SEM models. The sample size used in this study therefore satisfies both the heuristic guideline and the recommended statistical power requirements. To expedite data collection and achieve a wide range of respondents, data for this study was collected through a web-based survey using Google Forms, disseminated through social networks such as WhatsApp, Telegram, and email, in addition to professional networks such as LinkedIn and industry associations.

3.2. Research tool

This study assesses critical factors utilizing tools that have undergone validation and reliability testing in scholarly literature. Entrepreneurial mindset is defined using the (McGrath & MacMillan, 2000) scale, with five primary dimensions: opportunity recognition, innovativeness, risk management, growth orientation, and adaptability, with indications assessed via a 5-point Likert scale. Following adaptation, the researcher deconstructed

the indicators into nine question items.

The researcher employed the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) to assess the Resilience variable, focusing on adaptation, stress resistance, and recovery from adversity within organizational contexts (Connor & Davidson, 2003). Subsequent to modifications, the researcher produced six question items for this variable.

Self-Efficacy was derived from the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) by (Schwarzer & Warner, 2013), which assesses an individual's confidence in accomplishing demanding tasks through ten statement items.

Global human resources competence (GHRC) is assessed using the (Caligiuri & Tarique, 2012) framework, which comprises three primary indicators: cultural adaptation, global technical capability, and cross-border problem solving, aimed at encapsulating vital competencies for global competition. Following additional adaption, these indications are organized into 12 statement items. The utilization of these standardized instruments guarantees that the study construct is measured with validity and reliability, facilitating comparability with prior research outcomes. A detailed version of the research instrument, including all question-naire items, is provided in Appendix A.

3.3. Data analysis

The data in this study were analyzed utilizing the PLS-SEM methodology with the assistance of SmartPLS 4. The PLS-SEM was selected due to the researcher's conviction that it can effectively manage intricate models with a considerable number of indicators, making it appropriate for the study's characteristics. The analysis was conducted in two primary phases: first, assessing the outer model to evaluate the validity and reliability of the indicators; second, examining the structural model (inner model) to investigate the relationships between constructs or latent variables. SmartPLS 4 enables researchers to estimate parameters, assess significance using bootstrapping, and examine direct, indirect (mediation), and total impacts with enhanced flexibility and precision (Ramayah et al., 2018).

3.4. Outer model evaluation

This section outlines the criteria for evaluating the validity and reliability of constructs. Convergent and discriminant validity assessments were conducted. Convergent validity is assessed using two primary criteria: (1) the outer loading value of each indicator must exceed 0.7 to demonstrate a robust correlation

with its construct, and (2) the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) must surpass 0.5, indicating that the construct accounts for more than 50% of the variance in the indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity is assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, which involves comparing the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct to the correlations among other constructs. The criterion stipulates that the square root of the AVE must exceed these correlations to demonstrate that the construct is more closely related to its own indicators than to those of other constructs in the model (Hair Jr et al., 2014). This study employs three methods for assessing reliability: (1) Cronbach's Alpha, (2) Composite Reliability, with a threshold value of >0.7 for both metrics, and (3) Discriminant Validity with criteria of <0.90 (Sarstedt et al., 2022). Cronbach's Alpha assesses internal consistency among indicators measuring the same construct, whereas Composite Reliability offers a more precise estimation by accounting for the varying weights of each indicator, and Discriminant Validity that aims to ensure that each latent construct is empirically different from other in the model (Hair Jr et al., 2014).

3.5. Inner model evaluation criteria

The evaluation of the inner model in this study was conducted using several statistical assessments, including collinearity diagnostics using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), the coefficient of determination (R^2), the effect size (f^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), and path coefficient analysis for hypothesis testing. These procedures were employed to assess the explanatory power, predictive capability, and the significance of the relationships among the constructs in the proposed research model (Sarstedt et al., 2022).

To assess the mediating role of self-efficacy, this study followed the procedure proposed by Hair Jr. et al. (2014), which involves two main criteria. First, the indirect effect between the exogenous and endogenous variables through the mediator must be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Second, if the direct effect between the exogenous and endogenous variables is insignificant but becomes significant after the inclusion of the mediator in the model, full mediation is established. This indicates that mediator fully explains the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables (Ramayah et al., 2018). This approach ensures that the mediation analysis is conducted rigorously and in accordance with established methodological standards.

4. FINDINGS

4.1. Assessment of validity and reliability

Statistically, item was considered valid if its outer loading exceeded 0.70 (Cheung et al., 2024). Meanwhile, indicators with values below 0.70 were considered inadequate for convergent validity and were therefore excluded (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). Based on these measurement standards, the analysis results showed that in the entrepreneurial mindset framework construct, two indicators failed to meet the criteria: EM6 (0.656) and EM8 (0.688). Meanwhile, for the global human resource competence (GHRC) construct, four indicators fell below the threshold: GHRC8 (0.623), GHRC9 (0.689), GHRC11 (0.671), and GHRC12 (0.571). The RS1 indicator (0.552) for the

resilience construct was also invalid. For the self-efficacy construct, three indicators failed to meet the criteria: SE3 (0.623), SE4 (0.648), and SE5 (0.619). To meet construct validity criteria, the researchers eliminated indicators with outer loadings below 0.70 (Hair Jr et al., 2014). Although several indicators with outer loadings below 0.70 were removed, the conceptual coverage of the constructs was preserved because the remaining indicators still captured the key dimensions of each construct as supported by the theoretical framework.

After excluding indicators below 0.70, Table 1 shows that all remaining indicators met the threshold above 0.70 and were therefore valid.

Table 1: Summary of construct validity and reliability analysis.

Constructs	Outer Loading (Indicators)	Validity and Reliability
Entrepreneurial Mindset	EM1 = 0.787 EM2 = 0.875 EM3 = 0.892 EM4 = 0.861 EM5 = 0.824 EM7 = 0.773 EM9 = 0.749	CA = 0.921 CR = 0.937 AVE = 0.680
Resilience	RS2 = 0.828 RS3 = 0.881 RS4 = 0.874 RS5 = 0.836 RS6 = 0.791	CA = 0.898 CR = 0.924 AVE = 0.710
Self-Efficacy	SE1 = 0.703 SE2 = 0.759 SE6 = 0.828 SE7 = 0.805 SE8 = 0.812 SE9 = 0.789 SE10 = 0.802	CA = 0.897 CR = 0.919 AVE = 0.618
Global Human Resources Competence	GHRC1 = 0.865 GHRC2 = 0.862 GHRC3 = 0.870 GHRC4 = 0.815 GHRC5 = 0.865 GHRC6 = 0.785 GHRC7 = 0.774 GHRC10 = 0.740	CA = 0.931 CR = 0.944 AVE = 0.678

Source: Own elaboration.

Table 1 also indicates that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceed 0.50: Entrepreneurial Mindset (0.680), Resilience (0.710), Self-Efficacy (0.618), and Global Human Resource Competence (0.678). This data indicates that each construct contributes more than 50% of the variance in its indicator; thus, all constructs can be considered valid.

In terms of construct reliability, as shown in Table 1, all values meet the required reliability threshold (0.70). The Cronbach's Alpha values for Entrepreneurial Mindset (0.921), Resilience (0.898), Self-Efficacy (0.897), and Global Human Resource Competence (0.931) are all higher than 0.70. which shows that the constructs are very consistent with each other. Similarly, the Composite Reliability (CR)

value for each construct shows a value exceeding 0.90, which means that all constructs have high consistency in their measurement so that the four components in this model adequately meet the criteria for reliability and convergent validity.

4.2. Assessment of discriminant validity (HTMT)

Another facet used to determine construct validity is the measurement of discriminant validity that aims to ensure that each latent construct is empirically different from other latent constructs in the outer model. In this study, discriminant validity was assessed using the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion, stipulating that a construct demonstrates adequate discriminant validity if its value is below 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 2. Discriminant validity assessment using the HTMT criterion.

Dimensions	Entrepreneurial Mindset	GHRC	Resilience
Entrepreneurial Mindset			
Global Human Resources Competence	0.815		
Resilience	0.827	0.798	
Self-Efficacy	0.893	0.825	0.879

Source: Own elaboration.

Table 2 shows that all HTMT values are below the conservative threshold of 0.90. The highest HTMT value is 0.893, which is observed between entrepreneurial mindset and self-efficacy. These results explain that the construct measurements meet the required validity and reliability criteria, thus providing a solid foundation for further interpretation of the internal model.

4.3. Collinearity diagnostics

In Table 3 we present the result of the multicollinearity test. The VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is used to determine whether there is a multicollinearity problem among the independent variables in predicting the dependent variable.

Table 3. Results of Collinearity Diagnostics.

Dimensions	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
Entrepreneurial Mindset	2.324	<3	Acceptable
Global HR Competence	2.434	<3	Acceptable
Resilience	2.861	<3	Acceptable
Self Efficacy	2.356	<3	Acceptable

Source: Own elaboration.

The results indicate that all VIF values range from 2.356 to 2.434, which are below the critical threshold of 3 according to (Hair Jr et al., 2014). This finding suggests that there is no significant multicollinearity among the predictor variables in the structural model. Therefore, the model is considered acceptable and suitable for further structural analysis.

4.4. Coefficient of determination

This analysis measured the R-squared value,

Table 4. Coefficient of determination results.

Dimensions	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Global human resources competence	0.736	0.735
Self-Efficacy	0.702	0.701

Source: Own elaboration.

indicating the proportion of variance in the endogenous variable explained by the exogenous variables. Table 3 illustrates this issue effectively, with results indicating that the structural model has substantial explanatory power for the endogenous variables studied. The R-square score of 0.736 for the global human resource competence (GHRC) dimension indicates that 73.6% of the variability in GHRC is explained by the exogenous variables in the model, while the remaining 26.4% is influenced by external factors not accounted for in the model.

Meanwhile, the R-square value of 0.702 for the self-efficacy dimension indicates that 70.2% of the variance in self-efficacy is explained by the predictor variables in the model. Consistent with these results, the adjusted R-squared value (0.701), which is very close to the R-squared value (0.702), indicates that the model used is effective and free from overfitting, thus having substantial explanatory power, explaining the causal relationships between the constructs in this study.

4.5. Effect size (f²) and predictive relevance (Q²)

The f² value is used to determine the contribution

Table 5. The results of effect size (f²) and predictive relevance (Q²) analysis.

Exogenous	GHRC		SE		Threshold	
	F ²	Q ²	F ²	Q ²	F ²	Q ²
Entrepreneurial mindset	0.498	0.389	0.259	0.241	0.02 =small effect 0.15=medium effect 0.35=large effect	>0
Resilience	0.070		0.124			
Self-efficacy	0.319					

The results of Q² analysis shows that all endogenous constructs have Q² values greater than zero, indicating that the model has adequate predictive relevance. Specifically, the Q² value for self-efficacy is categorized as moderate, while global human resource competence demonstrates strong predictive relevance.

4.6. Model Fit

In this study, model fit evaluation focused on two

Table 6. Model fit evaluation result.

Dimensions	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	Threshold	Interpretation
SRMR	0.080 n	0.090	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≤ 0.10 → acceptable fit. ≤ 0.08 → very good fit 	Accaptable
NFI	0.733	0.729	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 0.90 → strong fit 0.70-0.90 → moderate fit 	Moderate

The results show that the SRMR values are 0.080 for the saturated model and 0.090 for the estimated model, indicating that the proposed model falls within the acceptable fit range. Furthermore, the NFI values of 0.733 for the saturated model and 0.729 for the estimated model suggest a moderate level of model fit, although the model has not yet reached the

of an exogenous variable to an endogenous variable in the structural model and Q² is employed to assess the predictive capability of the model in predicting endogenous variables. If the model has good predictive capability, the Q² value will be positive (Hair Jr et al., 2014). Based on threshold, the effect size (f²) analysis indicates that entrepreneurial mindset (EM) has a large effect on global human resource competence (GHRC) (f² = 0.498) and a moderate effect on self-efficacy (SE) (f² = 0.259). Resilience exhibits a small effect on GHRC (f² = 0.070) as well as on self-efficacy (f² = 0.124). Meanwhile, self-efficacy demonstrates a moderate effect on global human resource competence (f² = 0.319).

key indicators, namely the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) and the Normed Fit Index (NFI), which are widely applied in PLS-SEM. SRMR measures the discrepancy between the observed correlation matrix and the model-implied correlation matrix. An SRMR value below 0.10 indicates an acceptable model fit, while a value below 0.08 suggests a better fit. Meanwhile, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) evaluates the improvement of the proposed model relative to the null model, with values closer to 1 indicating a better model fit (Hair Jr et al., 2014).

category of a strong fit.

4.7. Hypothesis testing

This study examined seven hypotheses that correlated entrepreneurial mindset (EM), resilience

(RS), self-efficacy (SE), and global human resource competence (GHRC). Table 7 presents the outcomes of the hypothesis test. The coefficient value, t-statistic, and p-value show that the entrepreneurial mindset has a positive effect on GHRC. These values are $\beta = 0.147$, $t = 3.255$, and $p = 0.001$. This outcome means that the first hypothesis was supported. The second hypothesis was that resilience positively

affects GHRC, but the results did not support this. The p-value exceeded 0.05, which means that the hypothesis was rejected. Table 7 also shows the positive effect of an entrepreneurial mindset (EM) on self-efficacy (SE), which is indicated by evidence ($\beta = 0.515$, $t = 13.245$, $p = 0.000$).

Table 7. Summary of hypothesis testing and path coefficient estimates.

Hypothesis	Original Sample	Sample Mean	STDEV	T Statistics	P Values	Description
H1. EM -> GHRC	0.147	0.148	0.045	3.255	0.001	Support
H2. RS -> GHRC	0.082	0.082	0.044	1.871	0.062	Not support
H3. EM -> SE	0.515	0.516	0.039	13.245	0.000	Support
H4. RS -> SE	0.357	0.355	0.042	8.555	0.000	Support
H5. SE -> GHRC	0.665	0.663	0.041	16.325	0.000	Support

Source: Output of data processing by SmartPLS.

As shown in Table 7, fourth hypothesis is accepted, indicating that resilience has a significant impact on self-efficacy, as evidenced by the coefficient ($\beta = 0.357$), t-statistics ($t = 8.555$), and p-

value ($p = 0.000$). Furthermore self-efficacy has a significant effect on GHRC; therefore, fifth hypothesis is also accepted with values of $\beta = 0.665$, $t = 16.325$, and $p = 0.000$.

Table 8. Measurement of comprehensive indirect effect.

Hypothesis	Original Sample	Sample Mean	STDEV	T Statistics	P Values	Description
H6. EM -> SE > GHRC	0.342	0.342	0.034	10.150	0.000	Partial mediation
H7. RS -> SE -> GHRC	0.237	0.235	0.030	8.011	0.000	Full mediation

Table 8 shows the indirect effect measurement as proposed in the hypothesis. The analysis revealed that self-efficacy serves as a mediator between entrepreneurial mindset (EM) and global human resources competence (GHRC), showing a significant indirect effect ($\beta = 0.342$, $t = 10.150$, $p < .001$), which supports the mediation hypothesis. Following (Hair Jr et al., 2014) criteria, when the direct effect of exogent variable is significant, the mediating role of mediation variable is partial. The final hypothesis that examine the mediating role of self-efficacy between resilience (RS) and GHRC was confirmed by evidence ($\beta = 0.237$, $t = 8.011$, $p < .001$). Following established mediation criteria, these results indicate a case of full mediation, as the direct effect of resilience on GHRC was rejected.

5. DISCUSSION

This study describes empirical findings on factors influencing global human resources competence (GHRC). The first finding illustrates the significant influence of an entrepreneurial mindset (EM) on

GHRC, indicating that company employees with this mindset will have high adaptability and competitiveness in the global market. Therefore, to significantly improve company competitiveness, industrial management in Indonesia must strive to improve the entrepreneurial mindset of its employees. This finding aligns with the explanation, which states that an entrepreneurial mindset leads individuals to be prepared to take risks, encourage innovation, and be proactive, attributes that are crucial for effectively managing the complexities of globalization (Salis, 2023). Research conducted by Ali et al. (2025) and Vaivode (2022) also supports this finding, indicating that an entrepreneurial mindset significantly improves cross-cultural work competency and readiness to face global challenges.

The empirical test of the second hypothesis reveals that resilience does not exert a direct influence on GHRC. This indicates that, in Indonesia's industrial workforce, the existence of personal resilience alone does not guarantee an increase in global competence. Resilience appears to

function more as a latent psychological resource that requires reinforcement from other internal factors before it can be expressed in work-related capabilities. In this sense, resilience alone does not guarantee improved readiness to confront global demands, particularly when it is not accompanied by a strong sense of personal agency or confidence. This interpretation departs from earlier studies that portray resilience as a direct and universal predictor of employee performance (Santoro et al., 2021). Empirically, high work targets often exert pressure on Indonesian industrial workers, leading to the development of resilient individuals. However, they are also vulnerable in terms of their capacity or competence. Therefore, resilience alone is not enough capital to face global challenges because other reinforcing factors, such as self-efficacy, are needed for mental resilience to have a significant effect on increasing GHRC.

The hypothesis that entrepreneurial mindset (EM) has a positive effect on self-efficacy (SE) is supported by this study's findings, showing that the stronger a person's entrepreneurial mindset, the greater their confidence in facing challenges and making decisions. This finding aligns with the views of Bandura (2013) and Günzel-Jensen et al. (2017), who stated that self-efficacy is formed through an individual's experience in resolving complex situations – especially when grounded in a proactive, innovative, and initiative-driven mindset, as is the case in entrepreneurship. In the context of human resource development, an entrepreneurial mindset plays a crucial role in building a person's confidence to identify opportunities, overcome difficulties, and achieve goals independently (Pidduck et al., 2023). This study also supports the conclusions of Zampetakis et al. (2015) and Newman et al. (2019) that an entrepreneurial mindset can be a predictor of increased self-confidence in both professional and academic settings.

The fourth hypothesis was also confirmed that psychological resilience significantly influences a person's self-efficacy. The research findings corroborate the field's observation that highly resilient Indonesian industrial employees typically possess elevated self-efficacy, thereby establishing a robust foundation for cultivating globally resilient human resources. Therefore, Indonesian global industrial managers should help their workers become more resilient by giving them small tasks, useful feedback, and a safe place to work mentally. These results reinforce the theoretical framework proposed by Luthans et al. (2007) and Bullough et al. (2014) which stated that resilience builds self-efficacy

by helping individuals recover from failure and adapt to complex problems when facing an uncertain global work environment.

The results of the fifth hypothesis test confirm that self-efficacy significantly influences global human resource competence (GHRC). This finding demonstrates that industrial employees in Indonesia who have a strong sense of self-efficacy enhance an individual's capacity to navigate global complexities. Specifically, the research substantiates that employees in the Indonesian industrial context have strong individual confidence and have the ability to solve problems, make decisions, and achieve goals, which serves as a critical psychological foundation for developing the cross-cultural and dynamic competencies essential in today's global workforce. This finding suggests that industrial management in Indonesia should reinforce employee self-efficacy by providing directed autonomy, mastery experiences, and other supportive programs. According to Bandura's theory, self-efficacy is crucial in influencing individual motivation, perseverance, and job performance, particularly in high-pressure environments like the global labor market (Bandura, 2023). This finding aligns with earlier research, which highlighted that self-efficacy affects not just work performance but also work flexibility (Garcia, 2025) and long-term success in a competitive workplace (Davidescu et al., 2020).

The sixth hypothesis, which proposes the mediating role of self-efficacy in the relationship between an entrepreneurial mindset and global human resources competence (GHRC), was accepted. This finding supports the reality that industrial employees in Indonesia who possess strong self-efficacy will enhance their GHRC. So it is suggested to industrial management in Indonesia that they should reinforce employee self-efficacy when aiming to enhance their GHRC. This finding also demonstrates that self-efficacy acts as a psychological conduit between entrepreneurial mindset and GHRC. The entrepreneurial mindset (EM) has a substantial direct impact on GHRC, as outlined in the initial hypothesis; however, mediation path analysis uncovers a more compelling insight. When self-efficacy is included as a mediating variable, the influence of EM on GHRC increases substantially. This discovery reinforces prior research indicating that self-efficacy is a crucial psychological mechanism linking entrepreneurial traits with individual preparedness to navigate global complexities in the workplace (Wallin et al., 2021).

Hypothesis 7 is supported, indicating that self-

efficacy fully mediates the relationship between resilience and GHRC. This result demonstrates that resilience does not exert a direct effect on GHRC. In the context of Indonesia's industrial sector, employees with high levels of resilience do not automatically translate this at-tribute into enhanced GHRC. Rather, resilience contributes to GHRC only when it is accompanied by strong self-efficacy. This finding implies that managers in Indonesia's industrial sector should prioritize strengthen-ing employees' self-efficacy to foster the development of GHRC. While resilience reflects an individual's capac-ity to endure and adapt, self-efficacy serves as the critical mechanism enabling employees to effectively con-front and manage global challenges. This finding supports the prior research conducted by Cantante-Rodrigues et al. (2021), X. Wang & Ran (2025), and Nichols (2025).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and self-efficacy are factors shaping global human resource competency in the Indonesian industrial sector. The study's principal contribution is the identification of self-efficacy as a crucial mediator among entrepreneurial mindset, resilience, and global human resource competence (GHRC). Resilience, however, does not directly contribute to GHRC. From a theoretical perspective, this study supports the literature by integrating psychological mechanisms into the human resource competitiveness model, particularly in the context of developing countries.

Practically, these findings demonstrate the importance of developing human resource strategies that foster global competency through developing an entrepreneurial mindset, resilience and enhancing employee self-efficacy. Organizations should invest in programs that foster an entrepreneurial mindset, build resilience, and strengthen self-efficacy through various supportive activities such as intrapreneurship projects, opportunity recognition

training, and structured mentoring systems. Together, these interventions can create a more confident, adaptive, and competitive workforce in the global arena.

This study acknowledges limitations that provide opportunities for future research. From a methodological standpoint, purposive sampling techniques may not entirely satisfy the randomness assumption inherent in PLS-SEM. As a result, the findings may have limited generalizability. Future research should employ probability sampling methods, such as simple random sampling or stratified sampling, to validate and extend the proposed model.

7. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION

This study provides actionable insights for organizations in strengthening global human resource competence through the development of entrepreneurial mindset and resilience, with self-efficacy playing a critical mediating role. Managerial relevance lies in the need to move beyond technical skill development to-ward fostering adaptive cognitive and psychological capabilities. Organizations are therefore encouraged to design structured interventions, such as innovation-driven training, experiential learning, and resilience-building programs, to cultivate proactive and adaptable employees.

Furthermore, enhancing employees' self-efficacy is essential to maximizing these effects. Managers should focus on reinforcing individual confidence through constructive feedback, recognition systems, and challenging yet attainable task assignments. At a strategic level, integrating these dimensions into perfor-mance management and talent development systems—alongside global competencies such as cross-cultural communication and digital literacy—will enable organizations to build a more competitive and future-ready workforce in the global industrial landscape.

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